

A REVIEW ON SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS' SELF-EFFICACY BELIEFS AND LEADERSHIP STYLES

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Abstract

This review examines the relationship between the self-efficacy beliefs and leadership styles of school administrators. This study reviews the importance of school administrators' self-efficacy beliefs in achieving the schools' goals. The study emphasizes the significance of the leadership role of school administrators in modern educational administration approaches. The study also argues that to demonstrate the school administrators' expected function, they must have a healthy perception of being "an effective administrator." Furthermore, the study concluded that the self-efficacy beliefs of the administrators make a difference in their leadership style; there is a relationship between self-efficacy beliefs and exhibiting transformational leadership behaviors, and the more school administrators feel efficient.

Keywords: self-efficacy beliefs, school administrators, leadership style, transformational leadership

Introduction

School administrators play a vital role in shaping culture, climate, and quality of education in their schools. Their role is to lead, manage, and inspire their stakeholders and deal with multiple challenges and demands from different stakeholders. To perform these tasks effectively, school administrators need to have a high level of self-efficacy, defined as "the belief in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments" (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy influences how people think,

feel, and act, affecting their motivation, perseverance, and resilience in the face of difficulties (Bandura, 1997).

However, self-efficacy is not a static trait that school administrators possess. According to Bandura (1997), it is a dynamic and context-specific construct that can vary depending on the situation and the domain of activity. Therefore, it is imperative to examine how school administrators' self-efficacy beliefs are related to their leadership styles, which are patterns of behaviors and attitudes that they exhibit when interacting with others and influencing their followers (Northouse, 2019). Leadership styles significantly influence organizational climate, staff morale, student achievement, and school stakeholder satisfaction (Hallinger & Heck, 2010).

School administrators' leadership role is significant in the success of the school. A positive learning environment ensures that the school is well-managed and that students receive high-quality education. According to the study titled *The Leadership Performance of Private School Administrators of Higher Education Institutions* presented by Princesita Timonera et al. stated that "school administrators were found to be highly effective in all areas such as setting instructional direction, teamwork, sensitivity, judgment, results orientation, oral communication, written communication, developing others, and understanding own strengths and weaknesses. They found highly effective leadership behavior such as communicating the school goals, supervising and evaluating instruction, coordinating the curriculum, monitoring student progress, protecting instructional time, maintaining high visibility, providing incentives for teachers, promoting professional development, and providing incentives for learning."

School Administrators' Self-Efficacy Beliefs and Leadership Styles

Self-efficacy is associated with individuals' perseverance and determination to succeed in their tasks (Bandura, 1986). If one believes that an individual can determine successful results through effort and perseverance, this increases his/her performance and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1986). Bandura (1982) and Covington (1984) maintain that the success of self-efficacious individuals leads to greater efforts to achieve and persevere through difficult tasks. In general, self-efficacy beliefs refer to an individual's belief in their ability to perform a specific task successfully. In the context of school administration, self-efficacy beliefs refer to the administrators' perception of their ability to perform their assigned roles effectively.

Another study published in the *Journal of Educational Administration* found that principals' sense of efficacy influences their leadership style. Therefore, self-efficacy is an important factor in determining the leadership style of an administrator. School administrators' tasks involve managing an institution's environment, people, and program. These tasks require information, skills, and abilities from various disciplines; however, personal perception and motivation are needed to perform the task. According to Fisher, 2014, the self-efficacy of administrators is vital for school management. School administrators with high self-efficacy beliefs can lead and facilitate organizational expected roles and facilitate the exchange of ideas between the various systems in the institution.

On the other hand, **leadership** is “a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal” (Northouse, 2019). The relationship between population and self-efficacy beliefs and effective school leadership style has been studied extensively. In the study conducted by Cobanoglu and Yurek (2018), the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) developed by Bass and Avolio (1995) was used to measure the leadership styles of school administrators. The MLQ identifies three leadership styles: transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire. Transformational leadership is characterized by inspiring, motivating, and empowering followers to achieve higher levels of performance and satisfaction. Transactional leadership is based on exchanging rewards and punishments for compliance and performance. Laissez-faire leadership lacks leadership, resulting in low effectiveness and satisfaction levels.

Methodology

A study conducted in 2018 by Cobanoglu and Yurek aimed to examine the relationship between school administrators' self-efficacy beliefs and leadership styles. Another study conducted in 2019 by Acat, Ozyurt, and Karadag aimed to evaluate the self-efficacy levels of elementary school principals about legislation tasks.

This study used qualitative research design to investigate and evaluate the relationship between school administrators' self-efficacy beliefs and leadership styles using survey techniques and a questionnaire to collect data from school administrators. The study used The School Administrator's Self-efficacy Scale (SASES) and the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ). The SASES consists of 30 items that measure the self-efficacy beliefs of school administrators in four domains: instructional leadership, organizational leadership, human relations leadership, and external relations leadership. The MLQ was adapted from Bass and Avolio's (1995) original version to measure the leadership styles of school administrators in three dimensions: transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire. The MLQ consists of 36 items that assess the frequency of the behaviors and attitudes of school administrators as perceived by their teachers. A convenience sample of school administrators and teachers who work in state primary, secondary, and high schools. Selection of participants used a stratified random sampling method according to the geographical regions, school levels, and school types. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, t-test, ANOVA, and regression analysis for data analysis. The study used these methods to describe the variables' characteristics and distributions, examine the relationships and differences among the variables, test the hypotheses, and answer the research questions.

Reflecting on the following criteria in assessing data collection techniques and the study's reliability: First, the validity and reliability of the instruments. The study tested the validity and reliability of the SASES and the MLQ using factor analysis, Cronbach's alpha, and confirmatory factor analysis. The results showed that both instruments had satisfactory validity and reliability, as the factor structures were consistent with the theoretical frameworks, and Cronbach's alpha values were above 0.70 for all scales and subscales.

Second, the representativeness and generalizability of the sample. The study stated that it used a stratified random sampling method to ensure that the sample was representative of the school administrators' and teachers' population. However, they also acknowledged that the sample was a convenience sample, which means that the participants were selected based on their availability and accessibility rather than their probability of being selected. It may limit the generalizability and external validity of the results, as the sample may not reflect the characteristics and diversity of the target population. Third, the accuracy and completeness of the data. The study did not report any issues or problems with the data collection process, such as missing data, outliers, or measurement errors. It also did not mention any ethical or practical challenges they faced during the data collection, such as informed consent, confidentiality, or response rate. However, they did not provide any details or evidence to support the accuracy and completeness of the data, such as the sample's descriptive statistics, the distribution of the responses, or the quality control procedures. And lastly, the appropriateness and rigor of the data analysis.

The study conducted by Cobanoglu and Yurek, 2018, used various statistical methods to analyze the data, such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, t-test, ANOVA, and regression analysis. It also reported the results of the data analysis in tables and graphs and interpreted the research questions and hypotheses. However, the study did not explain or justify the choice and assumptions of the statistical methods, such as the significance level, effect size, or multicollinearity. The study also did not report or address any potential limitations or biases of the data analysis, such as the confounding variables, the interaction effects, or causal inference.

Results

The study about administrators' self-efficacy and leadership style reveals important insight that can help school administrators improve their leadership styles in several ways. School administrators should aim to improve their self-efficacy beliefs in all four sources that Bandura (1997) proposed: mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and physiological and affective states. The school administrators should build a better connection and relationship with those they work with and often see.

School administrators had the highest self-efficacy in instructional leadership and the lowest in external relations leadership. This study found that the self-efficacy insight of the administrators makes a difference in their leadership style, and there is a relationship between the self-efficacy belief and exhibitors of transformational leadership behaviors; the more administrators feel efficient, the more they exhibit transformational leadership behaviors, Cobanoglu & Yurek (2018).

Another study aimed to evaluate elementary school principals' self-efficacy levels about legislation tasks. The study found that the self-efficacy levels of the school administrators were high in all areas, such as setting instructional direction, teamwork, sensitivity, judgment, results orientation, oral communication, written communication, developing

others, and understanding own strengths and weaknesses, Acat, Ozyurt, and Karadag (2019).

Based on the study conducted by McBrayer et al. (2019), they were also found to be highly effective in leadership behavior such as communicating the school goals, supervision and evaluation instruction, coordinating the curriculum, monitoring student progress, protecting instructional time, maintaining high visibility, providing incentives for teachers, promoting professional development, and providing incentives for learning.

This study showed that school administrators exhibited more transformational and transactional leadership behaviors than laissez-faire ones, but there was still room for improvement. It recommends that school administrators enhance their transformational leadership by articulating a clear and compelling vision, providing individualized support and recognition, fostering a collaborative and innovative culture, and modeling high standards and ethical values. School administrators should know the demographic factors influencing their self-efficacy and leadership styles and adjust their behavior accordingly.

Moreover, there were significant differences in self-efficacy and leadership styles according to gender, age, education level, experience, and school level. For example, female school administrators had higher self-efficacy and transformational leadership than male school administrators. In comparison, older and more experienced school administrators had lower self-efficacy and transformational leadership than younger and less experienced school administrators. The study advises that school administrators can overcome these differences by respecting and appreciating the diversity of their staff and students and by seeking continuous learning and improvement.

Discussion and Conclusion

School administrators experience some challenges in improving their leadership style. Recruiting, retaining, and developing qualified and motivated teachers and staff is one of their biggest challenges. School administrators must create a positive and supportive work environment, provide adequate resources and professional development opportunities, and recognize and reward good performance. Balancing multiple and competing demands and expectations from various stakeholders. School administrators must communicate and collaborate with different groups, such as students, parents, teachers, staff, district officials, policymakers, and community members, and respond to their diverse and sometimes conflicting needs and interests. However, they might face challenges in managing their time and resources. Prioritizing their goals and actions can be another challenge administrators are experiencing. Resolving conflicts and tensions among stakeholders might be one of their challenges. Leading and managing change and innovation in a complex and uncertain environment is another challenge for school administrators. They need to adapt and respond to the changing needs and demands of society, the economy, and the education system and to foster a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in their schools. Developing and maintaining their own professional identity, competence, and well-being.

In conclusion, school administrators need to have a clear and strong sense of who they are, what they do, and why they do it, and to update and enhance their professional knowledge and skills constantly. They must also care for their physical, mental, and emotional health and balance their personal and professional lives.

School administrators can enhance their self-efficacy by engaging in more professional development activities, seeking feedback and support from their colleagues and superiors, and reflecting on their successes and failures. School administrators should adopt a more transformational leadership style, which was positively associated with self-efficacy and school effectiveness.

The relationship between administrators' self-efficacy and leadership style is an important area of research in educational administration. Studies have shown a significant relationship between perceived self-efficacy belief and leadership style. The more administrators are efficient, the more they exhibit transformational leadership behaviors (Cobanoglu & Yurek, 2018). School administrators' effective leadership skills and behaviors have a positive relationship with school performance. Demonstrating effective leadership skills and behaviors among school administrators can strengthen student learning by motivating teachers, staff, and students.

There are areas for improvement in this study that need to be acknowledged and addressed in future research. One of the limitations is that the study used a cross-sectional design, which means that the data were collected at one point in time. It limits the ability to establish causal relationships between self-efficacy, leadership styles, and school effectiveness and examine these constructs' changes and dynamics over time. Another area for improvement is that the study relied on self-report measures, which may introduce some biases and errors in the data. For example, the participants may have responded to the questions based on their social desirability, impression management, or self-enhancement motives rather than their actual beliefs and behaviors.

Moreover, the participants may have different interpretations and understandings of the items and scales, which may affect the validity and reliability of the measures. A mixed-methods approach, which combines quantitative and qualitative data, would be more effective in triangulating and validating the findings and providing a richer and deeper insight into the phenomena under investigation. Furthermore, lastly, the study used a convenience sample, which means that the participants were selected based on their availability and accessibility rather than their representativeness of the population because it limits the generability and external validity of the results, as the sample may not reflect the characteristics and diversity of the target population. A random or stratified sample, which ensures that the participants are selected based on a probability or a proportional criterion, would be more appropriate to enhance the generability and external validity of the results.

Recommendations

Future research on administrators' self-efficacy and leadership style should first explore and prioritize examining the causal effects of self-efficacy and leadership styles on school effectiveness, using experimental or quasi-experimental designs, such as randomized controlled trials, pretest-posttest designs, or difference-in-differences methods. These designs would allow us to manipulate and control independent variables (self-efficacy leadership styles) and (school effectiveness) over time and across groups. Secondly, to explore the mediating and moderating mechanisms and factors that may influence the relationship between self-efficacy, leadership styles, and school effectiveness, using structural equation modeling, path analysis, or multilevel modeling. These methods would enable us to test and estimate the direct and indirect effects of the variables and account for the nested and hierarchical structure of the data (for example, teachers within schools, schools within a district). Lastly, to investigate the contextual and cultural variations and similarities of self-efficacy, leadership styles, and school effectiveness, using cross-cultural or comparative studies, such as surveys, interviews, or case studies.

Future researchers can consider alternative data collection techniques such as observation, focus group discussion, and case studies. These data collection techniques provide rich and detailed data on actual practices and processes of school leadership and the contextual and situational factors that may affect them. It can elicit diverse data on the participants' opinions, attitudes, feelings, and perceptions and the group dynamics and interactions that may influence them. Focus group discussion can generate new ideas and insights that may not emerge from individual interviews or surveys. Case studies can also provide a rich and holistic understanding of the case or phenomenon and its context, complexity, and uniqueness. It can also explore the causal mechanisms and processes that underlie the case or phenomenon and the variations and similarities across different cases or phenomena. However, these data collection strategies have some limitations and drawbacks, such as difficulty selecting and defining cases, difficulty recruiting and managing participants, difficulty gaining access and trust, and the possibility of observer bias or influence and other possible difficulties.

These studies would provide a broader and deeper understanding of how self-efficacy and leadership styles are shaped and expressed by different social, political, and economic factors and how they affect and are affected by different educational systems, policies, and practices. These also provide a new aspect and open a new possible environment that leaders can tackle upon providing and improving connections and relationships. These studies are a stepping stone into reflection and adaptation towards different environments and factors that affect systems, policies, and practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

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